

D6.1

Website and project logo

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Project Details

Acronym: **MultiSpin.AI**

Title: **n-ary spintronics-based edge computing co-processor for artificial intelligence**

Coordinator: Bar Ilan University (Israel)

Reference: 101130046

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Duration: 36 months

Consortium:

Id	Participant Name	Short name	Country
1	BAR ILAN UNIVERSITY	BIU	ISRAEL
2	INESC MICROSISTEMAS E NANOTECNOLOGIAS - INSTITUTO DE ENGENHARIA DE SISTEMAS E COMPUTADORES PARA OS MICROSISTEMAS E AS NANOTECNOLOGIAS	INESC MN	PORTUGAL
3	UNIVERSITE CATHOLIQUE DE LOUVAIN	UCLouvain	BELGIUM
4	SPINEDGE LTD	SPINEEDGE	ISRAEL
5	INTERACTIVE FULLY ELECTRICAL VEHICLES SRL	IFEVS	ITALY
6	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	VUB	BELGIUM

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	5
1 Introduction	6
2 Background	6
3 Logo and graphic charter	6
3.1 Supplier selection	7
3.2 Design process	7
3.3 Delivered materials	7
4 Website	8
4.1 Supplier selection	9
4.2 Website design and creation	9
5 Conclusion	10

Executive Summary

The MultiSpin.AI project aims to revolutionize neuromorphic computing. With a consortium comprising leading research institutes, universities, and SMEs, the project endeavours to create highly efficient chips capable of performing AI algorithms at unprecedented speeds while reducing energy consumption. This transformative technology holds the potential to revolutionize various sectors, including autonomous vehicles, robotics, and medical devices, while contributing to the EU's chip industry and reducing CO2 emissions from AI inference.

To effectively communicate the vision, objectives, and progress of the project, the creation of a graphical charter, logo, and comprehensive website was imperative. These components serve as cohesive representations of the project's identity and aspirations, facilitating engagement with stakeholders, dissemination of research outcomes, and fostering collaboration within the scientific community and beyond.

The establishment of a visual identity, including the logo and graphical charter, was undertaken to encapsulate the nature of MultiSpin.AI and symbolize its role in revolutionizing neuromorphic computing. Additionally, the development of a comprehensive website tailored specifically for MultiSpin.AI serves as a centralized hub for stakeholders to access project updates, resources, and information.

Supplier selection for both the graphical charter/logo and website development was meticulous, with L'Artisane emerging as the ideal partner. Their efficiency, high-quality outputs, and commitment to eco-design principles resonated strongly with the project's objectives, ensuring timely delivery and adherence to schedule requirements.

In conclusion, the establishment of a visual identity and online presence represents a key step towards effective communication and engagement for the MultiSpin.AI project.

1 Introduction

To effectively communicate the vision, objectives, and progress of the MultiSpin.AI project, the creation of a graphical charter, a logo, and a comprehensive website was imperative. These essential components will serve as cohesive representations of the project's identity and aspirations, facilitating engagement with stakeholders, dissemination of research outcomes, and fostering collaboration within the scientific community and beyond.

2 Background

MultiSpin.AI is a fundamental research project that is set to run for three years starting in February 2024.

MultiSpin.AI aims to revolutionize neuromorphic computing by creating highly efficient chips capable of performing AI algorithms like Deep Learning at unprecedented speeds while drastically reducing energy consumption, ultimately enabling transformative applications like autonomous vehicles, robots, and medical devices, and contributing to the EU's chip industry and reducing CO2 emissions from AI inference.

The project involves several participants:

1. Bar Ilan University - Israel (Coordinator)
2. INESC Microsistemas e Nanotecnologias - Instituto - Portugal (Partner)
3. Universite Catholique de Louvain - Belgium (Partner)
4. SpinEdge - Israel (Partner)
5. Interactive Fully Electrical Vehicles SRL - Italy (Partner)
6. Vrije Universiteit Brussel - Belgium (Partner)

These organizations - leading research institutes, universities, and SMEs - are coming together to delve into revolutionary research that aims to transform how AI is processed and utilized. They will collaborate across various expertise areas, from material sciences to AI development and ethics, to collectively simulate, fabricate, characterize, and integrate spintronic hardware with AI algorithms, ensuring both technical advancement and ethical considerations in the development process.

3 Logo and graphic charter

With the launch of the MultiSpin.AI research project emerged the necessity for a cohesive visual identity to represent its objectives and achievements effectively.

Our endeavour encompassed the creation of a logo that encapsulates the nature of MultiSpin.AI, symbolizing its role in revolutionizing neuromorphic computing. This logo will not only serve as a visual marker but also as a representation of the project's goals and potential impact. Moreover, the development of a comprehensive visual identity, spanning stationery, conference materials, signage, and decorations, will ensure consistent branding across various communication channels.

Additionally, the formulation of visual guidelines tailored for social media channels will enable the project to maintain a unified and impactful online presence.

The target audiences for these visual elements encompass a wide spectrum of stakeholders. Scientific communities, comprising researchers across international labs and institutions, seek innovative solutions like MultiSpin.AI for diverse applications. Industry stakeholders, including chip makers, device manufacturers, and end customers, are drawn to the project's potential for technological advancement and collaboration opportunities. Policymakers, on

D6.1 Website and project logo

the other hand, are interested in the legal, ethical, safety, and security implications of MultiSpin.AI applications. Lastly, the general public, particularly technology adoption innovators, represents potential end-users or beneficiaries who are intrigued by the project's promise of improved accuracy, privacy, and eco-friendly energy efficiency.

Through the creation of a compelling logo and graphical charter, MultiSpin.AI aims to establish a visual identity that resonates with its diverse audiences. These visual components will serve as tools for communicating the project's objectives, values, and potential impact, reinforcing its position in the field of neuromorphic computing.

3.1 Supplier selection

Following a selection process to identify a supplier for creating the logo and graphical charter for MultiSpin.AI, L'Artisane, a French communication agency based in Rennes, emerged as the optimal choice. L'Artisane surpassed other candidates by demonstrating efficiency and cost-effectiveness in their approach. In addition to their efficiency, L'Artisane's ability to deliver high-quality outputs within timely constraints played a role in their selection.

3.2 Design process

After selecting a supplier for the creation of the logo and graphical charter, MultiSpin.AI WP6 conducted multiple meetings with the supplier to define the work horizon. Following this, the supplier presented the initial design, which WP6 shared with consortium members for their feedback. Utilizing the insights gleaned from the consortium members' comments, the supplier iteratively refined the design of the logo and graphical charter. Upon completion of the design phase, the supplier proceeded to finalize and provided the logo and graphical charter. This collaborative methodology streamlined the development process and ensured that the logo and graphical charter effectively represented the MultiSpin.AI project.

Given our iterative methodology, we engaged our partner repeatedly to incorporate adjustments and integrate suggestions from consortium members. Ultimately, this process resulted in the creation of four distinct versions.

- A first version was suggested on February 7, 2024
- A final version was received on March 20, 2024

3.3 Delivered materials

The logo and graphic charter include:

- MultiSpin.AI's logo (three versions)
- Colors, typography and patterns
- Icons & maps
- Business cards
- Envelopes
- Letterheads
- Note cards
- Bookmarks
- Conference materials: badges, kakemonos
- Social media and presentation templates

D6.1 Website and project logo

Main colors

Main fonts

Nunito Sans Semi Bold:
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789
 -./:!

Nunito Sans Extra Light:
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789
 -./:!

Actey Regular:
 abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
 ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
 0123456789
 -./:!

Patterns

Icons

Maps

Letterhead

Business card

Envelope

Note card

Badges

Bookmark

Presentation

Kakemonos

Template

4 Website

As the MultiSpin.AI project progresses towards its operational phase, the imperative to establish an online presence through a dedicated website became increasingly apparent. With the objectives, guidelines, building blocks, and funding nearing completion, the focus lied towards creating an engaging and informative digital platform to showcase the project's objectives and achievements.

The task at hand entailed the creation of a website tailored specifically for MultiSpin.AI, serving as a centralized hub for stakeholders to access project updates, resources, and information. This website will not only provide a platform for disseminating project-related content but also serve as a conduit for fostering collaboration and engagement among stakeholders.

D6.1 Website and project logo

In addition to the front-facing interface, attention was directed towards developing a user-friendly backend for website administrators and editors. This backend system will streamline content management processes, facilitating efficient updates and modifications to ensure the website remains dynamic and up-to-date.

Furthermore, the establishment of a domain name and hosting solution is essential to ensure the website's accessibility and reliability. By selecting an appropriate domain name and hosting provider, we aim to optimize the website's performance and ensure seamless access for users across various devices and locations.

The implementation of an SEO strategy and robust security measures is paramount to enhance the website's visibility and protect against potential threats. By optimizing the website's search engine ranking and implementing stringent security protocols, we aim to safeguard sensitive information and maintain user trust and confidence.

4.1 Supplier selection

Following an open call to identify a supplier for the website and project development, L'Artisane, emerged as the ideal partner given their prior engagement in creating the project's logo and graphical charter. Their track record in communication and design, coupled with their commitment to eco-design principles, resonated strongly with the project's objectives. Eco-design encompasses the integration of environmental considerations into the design process, ensuring that the final product minimizes environmental impact throughout its lifecycle.

Furthermore, L'Artisane's demonstrated ability to deliver high-quality outputs within tight deadlines set them apart from other candidates. Given the project timeline, their capacity to meet our schedule requirements was instrumental in the decision-making process.

4.2 Website design and creation

Following the selection of a supplier for the website creation, MultiSpin.AI WP6 provided the supplier with a structured framework, initially approved by the MultiSpin.AI project coordinator. Subsequently, the supplier presented the initial design, that WP6 shared to the consortium members for feedback. Leveraging the insights gathered from the consortium members' comments, the supplier iteratively refined the website design. Upon finalization of the design phase, the supplier proceeded to launch the website online. This collaborative methodology facilitated the development of the website.

During the content production phase for the website, our team also focused on crafting textual material intended for integration across various pages of the platform. This task necessitated close consultation with consortium members to ensure the validity and relevance of the content. Specifically, we engaged scientists within the consortium to verify the completeness and accuracy of the simplified scientific information. Simultaneously, we implemented a comprehensive questionnaire that all consortium members were required to complete. This approach enabled us to gather essential information about their respective organizations and personnel involved in the project. These data were instrumental in enriching and completing certain sections of the website, thereby ensuring a comprehensive representation of the consortium and its activities.

Once more, our iterative approach throughout this phase led to the creation of multiple versions of the website:

- An initial version was suggested on February 20, 2024
- A second version was suggested on March 5, 2024
- A third version was suggested on March 13, 2024
- A fourth version was suggested on March 23, 2024
- The final version online on April 4, 2024

This website is available on <https://multispinai.eu>.

D6.1 Website and project logo

5 Conclusion

MultiSpin.AI established a visual identity and online presence that resonates with its diverse stakeholders.

The creation of a graphical charter and logo, coupled with the development of a comprehensive website, signifies a pivotal step towards effective communication and engagement. These components serve as cohesive representations of the project's identity and aspirations, facilitating dissemination of research outcomes and fostering collaboration within scientific communities, industry stakeholders, policymakers, and the general public.

As the MultiSpin.AI project progresses, these visual elements and online platforms will continue to play a key role in amplifying its impact, fostering collaboration, and driving meaningful advancements in neuromorphic computing.